

INNOVATIVE STRUCTURAL AND TECHNOLOGICAL SOLUTIONS FOR CRANE-FREE ERECTION OF LARGE-SPAN COATINGS

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***Abstract.** The article presents an analysis of the known variant of lifting the coating by pulling. Taking into account the disadvantages and advantages of the considered technology, a new structural and technological solution for the construction of coatings by lifting modules has been developed. According to the new solution, the crossbars of the coating structures are enlarging at low scaffolding, then moved in the space between the paired columns of the frame by pushing with supports on the lifting modules. Guide profiles fixed on inner surfaces of paired columns are provided for vertical movement of modules. The process of pushing the coating consists of repeated cycles. Each cycle includes two stages. At the first stage, load from coating is taken up by lower platforms of module. For this purpose, sliding support cylinders of lower platform of module are placed in holes of guide profiles. Upper module platform and roof girders are moved to height corresponding to stroke of module hydraulic cylinders rods. At the second stage, load from coating is taken up by upper platforms of module. For this purpose, retractable support cylinders of the upper platform of the module are placed in holes of guide profiles. Lower platform of module is raised to height corresponding to stroke of module hydraulic cylinders rods. After lifting the coating to the design height and fixing the bearing*

girders between the heads of the paired columns of the frame, the lifting modules are lowered onto the foundations and dismantled. Optimization of the processes of lifting the coating is achieved by reducing the list of installation works to the operations for the final fixing of the coatings at the design height and the ejection of the roof girders by lifting modules from the foundation level to the design height in automatic mode.

Keywords: *lifting modules, erection of large-span coatings, structural technological solutions, pull-up method, load-bearing frame*

Problem formulation. The current state of the construction industry requires addressing issues related to further improving known and creating fundamentally new structural-technological solutions for the erection of large-span coatings. Today, the installation of coating structures is envisaged in two sequential stages. In the first stage, coatings are assembled and components of the building's load-bearing frame (foundation cups, columns, inter-column beams, and ties) are installed using low scaffolding with boom cranes by the free-lift method). In the second stage, the forced movement of the coatings is performed using the pull-up method with hydraulic jacks and guides ($\leq 90^\circ$), or by pushing with the coating supported on the lifting jacks [1]. For the pull-up method, a discrete lifting process is mandatory. Numerous stops are associated with the delivery and subsequent fixing in the installation zone of the structural elements involved in pulling the coatings. Additionally, interruptions in the lifting process are caused by delays necessary for arranging installation height platforms [2]. Improving structural-technological solutions for the erection of large-scale coatings using lifting modules, which optimize lifting processes and shorten overall coating lifting times, is a pressing issue for the development of the construction industry.

Analysis of recent research and publications. Famous domestic and foreign scientists paid great attention to the study of the peculiarities of the construction of reinforced concrete and metal coatings using traditional crane and craneless technologies. Thus, the organizational and technological solutions for the installation

of large-block industrial buildings and structures by free-lifting methods are described in detail in the works Tonkacheiev G.M. [3-5], Osypov O.F. [6], Chernenko K.V. [7], Sobko E.T. [8]. The stages of consolidation and lifting of the coatings using crane technologies are reflected in the works Yang Y. [9], Ruan R. [10], modern variants of the pull-up method and the push-out method Fagoli Asotech [11], Sarens group [12], DLT Engineering [13], MAMMOET [14], ENERPAC [15], ULTRACON [16]. In the scientific works of the mentioned authors and in the presentation materials of the manufacturers of modern lifting equipment, the processes of consolidation and lifting of coverings are described in detail, but there is no algorithm for optimizing structural and technological solutions for erecting coverings using lifting modules.

Purpose and tasks of the article. A systematic and comprehensive analysis of the features of the option of lifting coatings by the pulling method allows to accept the advantages and disadvantages of the implemented project for the development of the latest structural and technological solution for the erection of long-span coatings with mechanized technological equipment in the form of lifting modules, which would ensure the optimization of lifting processes and the reduction of the overall duration of works on the erection of long-span structural -technological blocks of coatings.

Presentation of basic material. The technology of lifting the coating by the pull-up method, with hydraulic jacks located on the tops of the frame's load-bearing columns, was used in the construction of the aviation plant workshops in Hostomel, Ukraine. The coating consisted of blocks measuring 96 x 48m and 96 x 54m and weighing 1100-1200 tons. Lifting two roofing blocks (total area 40,000 m²) to a height of 34 m was completed in 10 shifts [7]. PSH-330 hydraulic jacks, positioned on the tops of the design columns, performed cyclic pulling of the coating beams using a hinged-chain traction belt. The traction belt was hinged to the beam of the lifted coating. Load-bearing columns of the frame with intermediate platforms for temporarily supporting the coating block during movement to the design height

served as support structures for the hydraulic jack. Each block's lifting process consisted of six repeated cycles. Each cycle included two sequential stages – lifting the coating block by 6m and intermediate support of the coating on the column's supporting platforms. In each lifting cycle, the coating was pulled up six times to a height of 1m, corresponding to the stroke of the jack rods and the step of the holes in the traction belt. During the coating lift in the inter-column space, grille elements were dismantled in the section with a height of 6m, followed by the assembly of grilles after lifting the coating beam. The considered jack had a complex structure. Processes of dismantling grilles between paired columns for the passage of the support beam and post-lift securing of the inter-column grilles and operations for dismantling the links of the traction belts were complex and labor-intensive. The lifting process of the coating by the pull-up method and the fixation unit of the lifted coating beam are shown in Fig.1.

Fig. 1. Lifting of a long-span coating by the pulling method:

(a) – coating in the process of lifting, (b) – fixing unit of the supporting bolt of the lifting coating, 1 – block of coating, 2 – rack of the coating truss, 3 – upper belt of the coating truss, 4 – supporting crossbar of the coating, 5 – supporting frame column, 6 – lifting module PSH-330, 7 – lift support, 8 – intermediate lifting stop, 9 – traction belt, 10 – transition link of traction belt, 11 – slinging traverse

Maintenance of the step jack, its assembly, and dismantling at a height of 34m were inconvenient and unsafe. The fixing of the PSH-330 jacks at a height of 34m before lifting the coating and their dismantling after fixing the coating at the design height was carried out using powerful self-propelled crawler cranes with the condition of arranging roads around the building perimeter for crane movement 6m wide. The advantages of the analyzed solution include the formation of a rigid transverse frame from load-bearing columns and inter-column beams, and control of the verticality of the coating lifting process, ensured by moving the supporting beams of the coating block between paired load-bearing columns.

Considering the advantages of the pull-up method, where paired frame columns served as guides for moving the coating beams to the design height, a new structural-technological solution for coating erection using lifting modules was developed. The new solution involves moving the load-bearing beams of the coating from the foundation level to the final design level within the space between paired frame columns, supported by lifting modules. In the process of pushing the coating beams, the lifting modules rely on guide profiles fixed to the inner surfaces of the frame columns. The lifting module consists of a double-acting hydraulic cylinder, lower and upper platforms, and safety rods. The body of the hydraulic cylinder is mounted on the lower platform of the module, while the piston rod of the hydraulic cylinder is attached to the upper platform of the module. Both the upper and lower platforms of the module are equipped with lifting fixation mechanisms with retractable support cylinders. The safety rods are attached to the upper platform of the module and pass-through sliding nuts, which are secured to the lower platform of the module. To support the lifting fixation mechanisms, guide profiles are provided, which are mounted on the inner surfaces of the paired columns of the frame. The overall view of the coating during the pushing process to the design height and the lifting module is shown in Fig.2.

Fig. 2. The erection of the covering by a lifting module located between paired columns:

(a) – general view of the covering during the lifting process; (b) – lifting module:

1 – column of the frame, 2 – cover, 3 – supporting beam of the cover, 4 – hydraulic cylinder, 5 – lower platform of the module, 6 – upper platform of the module, 7 – supporting frame; 8- insurance rods

The process of pushing the covering while supported on the lifting modules consists of repeated cycles. Each cycle includes two sequential stages.

First stage “Extension of the module's upper platform and the roof's support frame”. The extendable support cylinders of the module's lower platform are placed in the guide profile holes. The working fluid is supplied to the hydraulic cylinder housings, moving the module's upper platform and the roof support frame to a height corresponding to the stroke of the hydraulic cylinder rods. The extendable support cylinders of the module's upper platform are placed in the guide profile holes.

Second Stage “Lifting of the module's lower platform”. With the upper platform bearing the load of the lifted roof, the extendable support cylinders of the module's lower platform are removed from the guide profile holes. The module's lower platform is lifted to a height corresponding to the stroke of the hydraulic

cylinder rods. The extendable support cylinders of the module's lower platform are then placed into the guide profile holes, and the lifting cycle stages are repeated until the roof reaches the design height. *Organizational and Technological Sequence of Roof Construction*. The construction process according to the developed solution involves preliminary assembly of large-span roof structures at the foundation level using self-propelled cranes. Simultaneously, the load-bearing frame elements such as foundation cups, paired columns, intercolumn beams, and ties are installed. Guide profiles with holes are fixed on the internal surfaces of the paired frame columns. Mechanized technological equipment in the form of lifting modules is placed on the foundations in the intercolumn space. The support frames and load-bearing girders of the roofs are supported on the lifting modules. After all the works on the assembly of the large-span roof structures, installation of technological equipment, formation of insulation layers, and completion of the roof block at 100% readiness, it is lifted from the foundation level to the design height (34 m). Vertical movement of the roof is carried out with the support of the roof's support frame on the module's upper platform. During the lifting process, the load from the roof is alternately borne by the lower and upper platforms of the module, which interact with the guide profiles. Once the roof reaches the design height, the roof's support frames are finally fixed between the tops of the frame columns. The load-free lifting modules are then lowered to the foundations.

The sequential stages of the vertical movement cycle of the covering supported on the lifting module are shown in Fig. 3.

The processes of moving the roof structure to the design height with support on the lifting modules are fully automated. The only high-altitude work involving installers is the final fixing of the roof's load-bearing frames between the tops of the paired frame.

Fig. 3. Successive stages of the cycle of vertical movement of the coating with support on the lifting module: a – extension of the module's upper platform and the roof's support frame; (b) - lifting of the module's lower platform, 1 - hydraulic cylinder housing, 2 - hydraulic cylinder rod, 3 - lower platform of the module, 4 - extendable support cylinders of the lower platform, 5 - upper platform of the module, 6 - extendable support cylinders of the upper platform, 7 - safety rods, 8 - paired frame columns, 9 - guide profiles, 10 - load-bearing roof girder, 11 - roof support frame

Conclusions and perspectives for further development

Based on the analysis of the known method of lifting large-span roofs by pulling, a new structural and technological solution for roof construction using mechanized technological equipment in the form of a lifting module has been developed. According to this solution, the roof girders, pre-assembled at the foundation level, are moved to the design height in the space between paired frame columns by pushing, supported on the upper platforms of the lifting modules. During the lifting process, the lower and upper platforms of the module alternately rest on guide profiles fixed on the inner surfaces of the paired frame columns. The developed solution optimizes installation processes and reduces the duration of lifting works by minimizing the high-altitude operations involving installers to final fixing of the roof support frames at the design height and performing all operations for moving the roofs from the foundation level to the tops of the frame columns in an autonomous mode. The construction site dimensions do not exceed the dimensions of the erected large-span roof.

The developed mechanized technological equipment can be further used in the development of structural and technological solutions for moving large-size external wall panels, pre-assembled at the foundations, to heights greater than 34 m using guide profiles fixed on the frame columns. Additionally, with improved characteristics of the lifting modules, the developed solution can be used for lifting large heavy technological equipment weighing up to 1200 tons in production workshops where it is technologically impossible to move the equipment using cranes.

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